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Technology Education For Enhanced Creativity And Sustainable National Development

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ABSTRACT

Technology education promotes, improved national competitiveness, all-round development and the accompanying prosperity, just as new and appropriate technologies promote steady improvements in living conditions and drive productivity gains which ensure rising incomes. Consequently, the existence and sustainability of these are very desirable in Nigeria. This paper succinctly examines the nature and significance of technology education and its innovations, their relevance in sustainable national development, the perspective and prospects in Nigeria, the importance of sustaining technology education innovations, and draws conclusions thereon. Emphasis was given to the fact that promotion of sustainable and comprehensive development is better guaranteed when matters which revolve around science, technology and innovations (STI) are wholly considered and appropriately implemented.

Keywords: Technology education, innovation, science and technology, sustainable development

INTRODUCTION

In many countries of Africa, innovations and breakthroughs made possible by science and technology education world over can never be ignored; neither can their contributions to sustainable national development in these countries be denied. The contributions of scholars like Fensham (Notable Australian science educator) in the school curriculum is equally of prime importance. (Aikenhead, 2003). Education involves the socialization of individuals to become integral part of the society in which they live (Okojie, 2007). Education is derived from the Latin word “educare” meaning to bring out a child physically and mentally or to rear. There is a general definition that conceives education as all round development of an individual, physically, socially, morally, mentally, temperamentally, psychologically and spiritually. Any education that lives out any aspect of human development would be the worst. Therefore, education is not just what has been reduced to transmission of scientific knowledge but assimilation of skills and values. According to Fafunwa (1976), education is the process that prepares individual for the future. Education is expected to reflect in the life of the recipient a kind of behaviour that conforms with norms and values of his society. Functional education is therefore, that type of education necessary for inculcating values and skills for future challenges and for national development. That is to equip individuals with appropriate skills, abilities and attitudes that will enable individuals to live and contribute to the development of the society (NPE 2004).

In Nigeria, three main educational traditions are known to have flourished at various times. They include the Indigenous, Islamic and the Western education, with each serving its purpose, amidst associated problems. The western-type of education, for the most part, has been the most successful in meeting the overall formal educational needs of citizens today and those that belong to tomorrow. It

began seriously in Nigeria with the arrival of the Wesleyan Christian Missionaries at Badagry in 1842 (FRN, 2014). Literary education in the 4Rs (reading, writing, arithmetic and religion) was predominant. Beyond this, the missionary education prepared the recipients for new job opportunities, with emphasis laid on character training. Today, technology education and its innovations are some of the dividends of western education.

Technology Education Innovations

Technology education is the study of technology which provides an opportunity for students to learn about the processes and knowledge related to technology, which are needed to solve problems and extend human potential (International Technology Education Association [ITEA], 2000). As a field of study, it covers the human ability to shape and change the physical world to meet needs, by manipulating materials and tools with techniques. Innovation on its own refers to the process of adding to or removing from an existing programme, new idea or method; with a view to improving the programme (Okeke, 1985).

A careful observation points to the fact that technological innovations and development cannot thrive without science and technology education. The interplay between the two becomes clearer when we remember that technology is science put into practical use to solve problems or invent useful tools. Tersely put, technology is the science of craft.

Africa, as we have today, is being driven by new scientific discoveries and technological breakthroughs. Consequently, broadening and sustaining the culture of science and technology and innovations is very important in Nigeria. To avoid lagging behind in developing capabilities to innovate, information that relate to science and technology must first be accessible to all levels of learning. The populace, especially, students, should be made to appreciate the fact that research can drive high technology innovation, and by extension, wealth creation.

On the global scale, innovations stemming from technological education have enabled countries like China, India, Korea, Singapore and Brazil to become fastest growing economies in the world and these innovations were made possible by outlandish investments in education and technological trainings. It then stands to reason that continuous improvement of the quality of technology education in Nigeria should be of paramount importance, since technology is the pivotal vehicle for industrialization and civilization.

Again, South Korea's automobile industry had humble beginnings. Its initial operations were merely assembling of parts from Japan and the United States, but it is today rated as one of the largest in the world in terms of production and export volume (Olalekan, 2014). Nigeria's case will not be different and we should not be afraid to start small. We can only reap the enormous dividends of technology education when we go beyond excellent formulation of policies and begin imbibing the culture of sincerity of purpose and total commitment and political will in the implementation of our laudable policies. Happily, there are a good number of automobile prototypes by Nigerian students and even artisans, meaning that a good support from government and private bodies could be the beginning of the journey to joining world manufactures of automobiles and accessories.

Sustainable National Development

Sustainable national development chiefly investigates and emphasizes the development of the present without compromising the future of the upcoming generations (Mensah, 2019). For sustainable development, teaching sustainability and making it a part of our daily living should become a predominant priority. Data covering the three pillars of sustainable development, viz economic, environmental and social data, needs be managed and deployed in an efficient and effective way to facilitate policy-making and decision-making that are rewarding.

Beyond this, our education system, especially as it relates to science and technology, should be tailored and directed towards solving our peculiar needs as a country. Instructions and information passed to students should be problem-solving oriented. It is of no use having heads filled with so much information and knowledge which are hardly ever translated or utilized in solving local problems. The students should be made to realize our needs and challenges as a nation. They should be encouraged to be extremely creative, think critically, be ready and determined to not just learn new things that could open up their minds to fresh ideas and knowledge, but to intelligently direct their education toward solving problems in their immediate environments, even as they think globally.

Sustaining Technology Education Innovations

Thus far, it can be clearly seen that broadening and sustaining the culture of technology innovations is needful. To do this well, we should remind ourselves again that information relating to technology must be accessible to all levels of learning, and citizens should be made to be fully aware that research can drive high technology innovations, which will in turn create wealth for the nation. Teaching sustainability and making it a part of our daily living is vital and equally one of the fastest ways to create awareness of the concept of sustainability for the upcoming generations. To achieve this, basic education must be restructured to address sustainability and expanded to include critical-thinking skills, skills to organize and interpret data and information, skills to formulate questions and the ability to analyze issues that confront communities (McKeown, 2002).

Again, technological learning and innovation capacity, which is critical in providing essential amenities to all, is fundamental in ensuring overall sustainable development (Thematic Think Piece, 2015). To understand this better, a country must develop its own capabilities to innovate, and the absence of such capabilities and their sustainability will mean limitations of such a country to apply existing technologies in all sectors, especially those at the front burner, such as health, agriculture and climate change.

While many nations around the world have embraced the need for education to achieve sustainability, a lack of vision and awareness has impeded progress in Nigeria, which can be partially attributed to lack of planning, proper supervision and implementation of well-designed policies. By addressing these critical issues, the Nigerian government can prevent or reduce delays or derailment of sustainable development projects and ultimately attain sustainability (Omole & Ozoji, 2014).

The challenges faced by ministries and agencies responsible for education of the youth, as well as data collection and sharing across the three pillars of development can be minimized by encouraging mobile learning and the use of mobile devices for communicating data and information. This is important when we remember that mobile devices enable contents to be presented in a format suitable for quick and easy comprehension by users. This will result in synergies and bring increased benefits with enormous potential for sustaining science and technology innovations.

In addition, since governments at various levels will find it difficult to raise the living standards of the citizenry in a sustained manner in the absence of better, cheaper and smarter ways of producing goods and making them available, they should, therefore, finance and provide incentives for science and technology innovations. Beyond these, they should adopt relevant means of sustaining such innovations.

Perspective and Prospects in Nigeria

In our rapidly-evolving world, science and technology education is an important instrument in the search for sustainable development and poverty reduction. It is, however, disheartening that governments at all levels in Nigeria have not really accorded science and technology education the necessary attention it deserves. Investments in adequate infrastructure, training and re-training of personnel, for instance, are significantly lacking. Again, the decline in science-related subjects, as shown in the performance of students in various examinations, is disturbing to say the least. These call for urgent steps to address the situation. There is also the need to exploit scientific discoveries outside Nigeria. At our slow rate of development, we need to rely on the world-wide reservoir of technical information available to the technological community (Akpomi, M.E., Dambo, B.I. & Ikpesu O.C., 2020).

The Nigerian government should not shy away from adequate funding and investments geared towards strengthening technology education at all levels of our education system, in conformity with global standards and practices. Nigerian teachers and students should be encouraged to embrace modern methods of teaching and learning at all levels of our education. In doing these, they should court educational technology, which involve the use of technology as a “tool” to enhance the teaching and learning process across all subject areas.

Adequate teacher education and competence of teachers, as being emphasized in various education sectors in different states of the country is also crucial. With forthrightness and determination, teacher education can still be salvaged from its apparent impending collapse. Proper interpretation and implementation of syllable and dedication to duty will also bring about appropriate teaching and good quality of teachers produced. In general, it is pertinent to note that attaining the sustainable

development goals will require educators to be willing to adopt scientific innovations that promote students' increased participation, collaboration and dynamism in the learning environment (Akpomi, 2009). Implementation of innovation is key, for it is one thing to adopt an innovation and another to implement it. Adoption of an innovation is the point at which the users express acceptance of the change, while implementation is the point at which the change is actually realized in the classroom (Rutherford, 1978).

CONCLUSIONS

New and appropriate technologies birthed by innovation will promote steady improvements in living conditions and productivity gains in Nigeria, which can be lifesaving for most citizens. We can only reap the enormous dividends of science and technology education innovations when we go beyond excellent formulation of policies and begin imbibing the culture of sincerity of purpose, total commitment and political will in the implementation of our laudable policies. Particular emphasis should be given to the connection between technology education, innovations, culture, and sustainable national development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The import of education innovations for sustainable development in Africa can never be overstressed and adopting the following will further enhance the process.

1. Broadening and sustaining the culture of technology innovations is needful for sustainable development in Africa, and African leaders should think towards this line.
2. Since no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers, teacher education shall continue to be given major emphasis in all educational planning and development.
3. In embracing education innovations, the cultural values of the society, its dynamics and changes occurring within the system should be minded, to uphold the goodwill and ethics of the society and transmit such to all stakeholders in educational systems of African countries.
4. To avoid Africa lagging behind other continents in developing capabilities to innovate, information that relate to science and technology must first be accessible to all levels of learning.
5. The populace, especially, students, should be made to appreciate the fact that research can drive high technology innovation, and by extension, wealth creation.
6. To match action to words, where required, government at appropriate levels should provide adequate funds for robust implementation of recommendations.

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